

D6.1 Review, analysis and crosswalk of the data requirements of key policies

Work Package	6
WP Co-Leader(s)	UNEP-WCMC; ISPRA
Deliverable Title	Review, analysis and crosswalk of the data requirements of key policies
Deliverable Number	D6.1
Deliverable Beneficiary	Aarhus University
Authors	Sabrina Agnesi, Adele Dixon, Sebastien Kaye, Oana Marin, Giulia Mo, Henn Ojaveer, Kristen Ounanian, Opi Outhwaite, Chris McOwen, Nadia Papadopoulou, Chris Smith, Hazel Thornton, Valentina Todorova, Carolina van Noort, Marina Venancio, Rowana Walton.
Internal reviewer(s)	Angel Borja and Laura Boicenco
Dissemination level	PU
Submission date	30 th November 2023
How to cite	Walton, R., Dixon, A., Kaye, S., Outhwaite, O., Agnesi, S., Marin, O., Mo, G., Ojaveer, H., Ounanian, K., McOwen, C., Papadopoulou, N., Smith, C., Thornton, H., Todorova, V., van Noort, C., Venancio, M. OBAMA-NEXT Deliverable 6.1. Review, analysis and crosswalk of the data requirements of key policies. 42 pp.
Title of project	Observing and mapping marine ecosystems – next generation tools
Instrument	HORIZON-CL6-2022-BIODIV-01-01
Contract number	101081642
Start date of project	1 December 2022
Duration	48 months
Project Coordinator	Jacob Carstensen

OBAMA-NEXT, OBSERVING AND MAPPING MARINE ECOSYSTEMS – NEXT GENERATION TOOLS (Grant Agreement: 101081642) project is funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe programme (grant agreement no. 101081642). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or UK Research and Innovation. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Table of Contents

Executive summary	5
List of figures	4
List of tables	4
List of abbreviations	5
1. Overview	6
1.1 The OBAMA-NEXT project.....	6
1.2 Purpose and overview of document	6
1.3 Understanding policy data needs to develop information products	6
1.4 Interlinkages within OBAMA-NEXT project to other tasks and deliverables	7
2. Key marine biodiversity legal and policy instruments	9
2.1 International marine biodiversity legal and policy instruments	9
2.2 European marine biodiversity legal and policy instruments.....	11
2.2.1 EU marine biodiversity law and policy	12
2.2.2 Regional Seas Programmes	14
3. Process to identify data needs and gaps in marine biodiversity policy	16
3.1 Selection of legal and policy instruments	16
3.2 Identification of policy data needs.....	17
3.3 Identification of gaps in information required in policy	19
3.4 Limitations of methodology	20
4. Data needs and gaps in information required for European marine biodiversity policy	21
4.1 Data needs required for European marine biodiversity policy	21
4.1.1 Biodiversity	21
4.1.2 Seafloor integrity.....	24
4.1.3 Other descriptors	24
4.2 Gaps in information required for European marine biodiversity policy	25
4.2.1 Biodiversity	26
4.2.2 Seafloor integrity.....	27
4.2.3 Other descriptors	28
5. Conclusion	29
6. References	30
7. Annexes	35
7.1 Annex A - Initial long-list of marine biodiversity related legal and policy instruments identified for analysis.....	35
7.2 Annex B – Final list of eight marine biodiversity related policy instruments analyzed	37
7.3 Annex C – Data needs categories by MSFD descriptors	38

7.4	Annex D – Keyword searches used for review of academic and grey literature.....	42
7.5	Annex E - Data needs required for reporting for European marine biodiversity-related Directives and Regional Sea Conventions categorised by MSFD descriptor	43

Executive summary

Monitoring the distribution and condition of marine species and habitats is crucial in successfully implementing and tracking the effectiveness of environmental policies in the European Union (EU). However, in many cases gaps exist in the data available making it difficult for Member States to undertake evidence-based actions and report their success. The “Observing and Mapping Marine Ecosystems-Next Generation Tools” (OBAMA-NEXT) project aims to utilise “next generation” technologies to address data gaps in marine and coastal environments within the European Union to support policy making, management actions and the health of ecosystems. The aim of this deliverable (D6.1) is to identify the data needed by Member States to implement and report against relevant European marine policy instruments, and highlight the gaps in the data available in order to ensure the information products developed within this project are of relevance to decision makers.

The analysis considered four EU Directives and four Regional Seas Conventions and Action Plans, which help to safeguard and recover marine species and habitats within the European Union. International policies were considered in the report but were excluded from the detailed analysis given their broader nature. To identify the data needs of selected policy instruments, the provisions of the main texts and their annexes were reviewed alongside their associated reporting templates. Guidance documents issued by the European Commission, decisions issued by the European Commission and monitoring manuals of the selected instruments were also reviewed. Data needs were categorized under the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) Descriptors, with species and habitats further categorized into ecosystem components to increase the specificity of data requirements. Gaps in the information available to meet the requirement of the instruments were identified through a literature review, to determine where data required for reporting on EU marine biodiversity policy are lacking.

The analysis found that species distribution and population demographics within the Biodiversity descriptor category were the most essential data needs as they were required across seven of the eight instruments considered. Data relating to marine mammals and seabirds were required by the highest number of instruments, whilst for habitats, data relating to benthic habitats in the infralittoral zone, including macroalgae and macroinvertebrate-dominated communities, coarse and mixed sediment, mud and sand, were required by the greatest number of instruments. Other critical data needs included bycatch of non-commercially exploited species, community composition of plankton, macrophytes and macrofauna, and measurements of nutrient and contaminant concentrations.

Data gaps were identified across all eleven MSFD Descriptor categories. Species distribution and population demographics (including population size) were identified as an essential data need and critical data gap, as was data relating to highly mobile species, such as turtles, and for relatively inaccessible habitats such as open waters and the deep sea. Time series data was a notable gap, primarily due to the complexities associated with

consistent monitoring of large geographic areas. This stresses the importance of forthcoming work on the information products and toolbox produced by the OBAMA-NEXT project in high priority thematic areas linked to species and habitat distribution.

In conclusion, the data needs inventory and identification of data gaps presented in this deliverable serve as a crucial foundation for the OBAMA-NEXT project. These findings are important for guiding the development of specific information products that will support the effective implementation of marine biodiversity policy within the EU. For example, data needs and gaps identified on species distribution within the MSFD Biodiversity descriptor category could be addressed by OBAMA-NEXT Task 4.3 (*Transforming data to fit-for-purpose tools, indicators and information products*) under Work Package 4. This deliverable emphasizes the importance of integrating these findings into other work packages within the project to maximize their impact on marine biodiversity policy. As the OBAMA-NEXT project moves forward, continued collaboration and focused efforts will be essential for addressing the data gaps within the scope of the project and enhancing the effectiveness of European marine biodiversity policy.

List of figures

Figure 1. OBAMA-NEXT project structure demonstrating the interlinkages of WP6 and associated tasks to the rest of the project. ----- 7

Figure 2. Workflow used to identify data needs and gaps in information in European marine biodiversity policy ----- 16

Figure 3. Example of the process for identifying data needs from specific sources for some of the target instruments.----- 19

Figure 4. Data needs required for reporting for European marine biodiversity related Directives and Regional Sea Conventions categorized by the Biodiversity descriptor from Marine Strategy Framework Directive ---- 22

Figure 5. Biodiversity data needs required for reporting for European marine biodiversity-related Directives and Regional Sea Conventions and Action Plans for different ecosystem components for population demographics/change in population demographics, species distribution/change in species distribution and habitat distribution/change in habitat distribution data -----23

Figure 6. Data needs required for reporting for European marine biodiversity related Directives and Regional Sea Conventions and Action Plans categorized by the Seafloor integrity Marine Strategy Framework Directive descriptor-----24

List of tables

Table 1: Documentation used to extract data needs for four RSCAPs and four Directives.----- 17

List of abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
BSIMAP	Black Sea Integrated Monitoring and Assessment Programme
BHD	Birds and Habitats Directives
CBD	Convention on Biological Diversity
CEMP	Coordinated Environmental Monitoring Programme
EU	European Union
EUNIS	European Nature Information System
HELCOM	Helsinki Commission
IPBES	Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
MPA	Marine Protected Area
MSFD	Marine Strategy Framework Directive
NbS	Nature-based Solutions
NDC	Nationally Determined Contribution
OBAMA-NEXT	Observing and Mapping Marine Ecosystems-Next Generation Tools
OSPAR	Oslo and Paris Convention
PAB	Practitioners Advisory Board
RSCs	Regional Seas Conventions
RSCAPs	Regional Seas Conventions and Action Plans
SCUBA	Self-Contained Underwater Breathing Apparatus
UNFCCC	United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change
WFD	Water Framework Directive
WoRMS	World Register of Marine Species
WP	Work Package

1. Overview

1.1 The OBAMA-NEXT project

The implementation of European environmental directives and the monitoring of the effectiveness of management actions, relies upon accurate mapping and monitoring of changes in a broad range of physical, chemical, and biological components. Such information is required to assess and track the health of marine species and ecosystems. It is needed to identify pressures, establish evidence-based measures to reduce these pressures and to evaluate the effectiveness of implemented management actions.

The Observing and Mapping Marine Ecosystems-Next Generation Tools (OBAMA-NEXT) project will develop toolboxes (utilising algorithms, models, data processing procedures and data streams), visualisations and information products to support the evaluation and communication of the status and trends of European marine ecosystems in an accurate, user-friendly and cost-effective manner. This will be achieved by developing tools that translate observations and knowledge into openly available information products to strengthen Europe's capability to acquire and use the data required to support the effective management of marine ecosystems and the services they provide.

These outputs will be relevant to Member States obligations under a wide range of national, regional, European and international policies, in particular the Regional Sea Conventions and Actions Plans, the European Green Deal, the European Union's (EU) Biodiversity Strategy for 2030, the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC), and the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework

1.2 Purpose and overview of document

This document details the data needed by Member States to implement and report against European marine policy instruments and highlights the gaps in the data available in order to ensure the information products developed by the OBAMA-NEXT are of relevance to decision makers. **Section 2** highlights the policy instruments that were identified and reviewed within this analysis. **Section 3** gives an overview on the methodology and approach that was used for the data needs analysis of marine biodiversity policy. Finally, in **Section 4**, the data needs and gaps in information in European marine biodiversity policy are identified.

1.3 Understanding policy data needs to develop information products

Under Task 6.1 'Review and evaluation of EU and international policy requirements' and this deliverable, the aim was to identify policy data needs to demonstrate the usefulness and relevance of the OBAMA-NEXT toolboxes (utilising algorithms, models, data processing procedures and data streams), visualisations and the information products to support marine biodiversity policy reporting and decision-making.

This was through the identification of regional, European and international marine biodiversity policies, directives and conventions where information products could inform the design, implementation, and monitoring of these instruments. Once these instruments were identified, the biodiversity data needs and gaps were determined. This allowed synergies across multiple instruments to be identified that could be addressed by the information products produced by the project.

Task 6.1 provides the foundation that will allow Task 6.2 (*Evaluation of the applicability of data products with respect to the EU/international policy needs*) to analyze the project’s information products, and outline their potential to support the design, implementation and monitoring of marine biodiversity assessments, policies and frameworks. Task 6.1 is also key to the rest of WP6 as deliverables D6.2, D6.3 and D6.4, all rely upon this baseline of data needs in order to demonstrate how the use of the information products can support the implementation of policy-driven Marine Protected Area (MPA) and Nationally Determined Contribution (NDC) objectives (Tasks 6.3 and 6.4 respectively). Task 6.5 will extend the understanding gained in this deliverable D6.1 to explore the enabling and constraining conditions of implementing these marine biodiversity policy instruments and how they can be more effective.

1.4 Interlinkages within OBAMA-NEXT project to other tasks and deliverables

WP6 and the tasks within it underpin all the other WPs within the OBAMA-NEXT project (Figure 1). Task 6.1 has created a continuous feedback loop with partners across WP’s 2, 3 and 4 to ensure the data products produced by the project will be compatible with the data needs identified in this policy analysis.

Figure 1. OBAMA-NEXT project structure demonstrating the interlinkages of WP6 and associated tasks to the rest of the project.

There is also a continuous relationship with WP1 and the Practitioners Advisory Board (PAB) formed under Task 1.1. Results from the online survey undertaken in Task 1.2 (*M1.2 PAB Online survey*) were taken into consideration when identifying the target policy instruments to be analyzed under this deliverable. In particular, the information collected in the survey on the instruments that stakeholders worked most closely with, the data required for reporting and the challenges associated with obtaining the data were considered. There has been a feedback process between Task 6.1 and D1.1 (*Initial specification information product catalogue fulfilling societal/policy needs*) to ensure that information products listed will address policy data needs identified in this deliverable. Task 3.5 (*Identify gaps and establish Best Practices*) and Task 4.1 (*Roadmap for technical solutions linking to user and policy needs*) will also use the policy data needs identified under this deliverable directly to ensure that the information products and toolbox created under this project link to these needs.

2. Key marine biodiversity legal and policy instruments

2.1 International marine biodiversity legal and policy instruments

At the international level a patchwork of treaty obligations and policy commitments are relevant to marine biodiversity in its broadest sense. Amongst other things, they seek to address biodiversity loss and climate change adaptation and mitigation, often through conservation and restoration measures. Whilst these are beyond the scope of this work, it is important to understand international policies, regulations and commitments due to their relevance to Member States of the EU (and other Contracting Parties) and because they feed in directly to EU law and policy.

The international law and policy framework provides, across numerous legally binding multilateral environmental agreements (MEAs), international soft-law instruments and voluntary instruments, obligations, commitments and priorities for contracting parties including, as applicable, the EU and its Member States. While national reporting requirements are a feature of MEAs, data needs tend not to be detailed or made explicit in the treaty text. For example, under article 4, the UNFCCC establishes that *“Parties should take action to conserve and enhance, as appropriate, sinks and reservoirs of greenhouse gases of all greenhouse gases not controlled by the Montreal Protocol, including biomass, forests and oceans as well as other terrestrial, coastal and marine ecosystems”* but this does not explicitly state the data needed for Parties to implement the provision or meet their reporting requirements under the Convention. More specific data needs may be elaborated subsequently through the work and decisions of MEA treaty bodies and expert groups. These may be highly influential but are not necessarily legally binding.¹ For example, the Conference of the Parties to the Convention on Biological Diversity at COP 9 (2008) adopted scientific criteria for identifying ecologically or biologically significant marine areas in need of protection (ESBAs) and COP 10 encouraged Parties to identify and adopt appropriate measures for conservation and sustainable use in relation to ESBAs. However, the selection of conservation and management measures is a matter for States and competent intergovernmental organizations to decide. Thus, particular data needs for a given Party will depend, at least partly, on national measures and priorities. The data needs for European marine biodiversity can in this sense often be understood to link to relevant international measures through the cascading of those commitments into regional (EU) and national (where applicable) policies and implementing measures (including legislation). Consequently, while the OBAMA-NEXT project proposal states that *“the project will identify key regional, European and **international** policies and frameworks... which require biodiversity-related data”*, given the scope and focus of OBAMA-NEXT, which focuses on the implementation and monitoring of European environmental directives,² the analysis presented in this report

¹ The legal nature of COP decisions and outcomes depends on the architecture of the parent Treaty. See for example Bodansky, D. (2016), The Legal Character of the Paris Agreement. *RECIEL*, 25: 142-150. <https://doi.org/10.1111/reel.12154>

² See OBAMA-NEXT project proposal number 101081642 Part B at 1.1

was directed specifically to data needs derived from EU marine biodiversity instruments, with the international framework referenced to provide broader context.

Whilst MEAs – notably the UN Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) and the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) – do not always separately or expressly address marine ecosystems their provisions do apply to them.³ Subsidiary agreements and instruments (such as the GBF, and COP decisions, for the CBD) however, do so more frequently. In terms of OBAMA-NEXT, key international commitments include:

- UNFCCC: Parties to take action to conserve and enhance sinks and reservoirs of greenhouse gases including oceans as well as other terrestrial, coastal and marine ecosystems.⁴
- CBD: General measures for conservation and sustainable use,⁵ obligations to establish in-situ conservation including through a system of protected areas⁶
- CBD Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Package: 30% of coastal and marine areas to be effectively conserved and managed by 2030,⁷ 30% of degraded marine and coastal ecosystems to be under effective restoration measures by 2030⁸, emphasis on NbS.⁹
- Sustainable Development Goals: SDG 14 - Conserve and sustainably use the oceans, seas and marine resources for sustainable development.

In addition, in June 2023 a new MEA on biodiversity beyond areas of national jurisdiction was adopted under the UN Convention on the Law of the Sea.¹⁰ The treaty has not yet entered into force and will apply to areas beyond national jurisdiction and has therefore not yet been implemented at EU or Member State level and is not assessed in this deliverable.

While specific data needs are not usually found in treaty text, the intergovernmental panels for climate change and biodiversity - respectively the International Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) and Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES) - provide technical and scientific assessments which aim to strengthen the science-policy interface and can feed into policy developments. The basis on which healthy marine ecosystems can help to meet international commitments on climate and biodiversity has been

³ For instance, Art. 8 Convention on Biological Diversity establishes obligations for in-situ conservation including “(a) Establish a system of protected areas or areas where special measures need to be taken to conserve biological diversity”.

⁴ Article 4.

⁵ Article 6

⁶ Article 8

⁷ Target 3

⁸ Target 2

⁹ Targets 8 and 11.

¹⁰ Agreement under the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea on the conservation and sustainable use of marine biological diversity of areas beyond national jurisdiction (New York, June 2023).

addressed by the corresponding intergovernmental panels, giving additional insights to the data needs and gaps in these arenas.¹¹ The IPCC, for instance, has elaborated on the relationship between marine ecosystems and climate change, recognizing *inter alia*, the importance of plankton in relation to climate mitigation and healthy marine ecosystems for climate mitigation and adaptation (Bindoff *et al.*, 2019). It highlights the need for NbS including marine protected areas and ecological restoration as well as sustainable fishing. With reference to restoration, the report also notes that blue carbon is seen as important for climate change mitigation and adaptation including through its role in carbon dioxide removal. Similarly, IPBES (2019) suggests possible actions for achieving the transformative change necessary for the conservation, restoration and wise use of biodiversity including, *inter alia*, expanding, connecting and effectively managing MPA networks and increasing protection and connectivity. Both bodies highlight the existence of data gaps, the need to improve decision-making and the need to enhance overall effectiveness when it comes to implementation. The Ocean and Climate Platform (2023), providing insights from the IPCC's Sixth Assessment Report (AR6) highlights the limited coverage of existing MPAs and their uneven distribution, with a subsequent need to improve MPA design and management and suggests data needs relating to the improvement of MPAs including decision-making for their designation, connection and management. The IPBES report highlights knowledge gaps in inventories of understudied ecosystems, including marine, and data on the comparative effectiveness of marine governance relating to conservation.

WP6 of the OBAMA-NEXT project (in particular Task 6.3 and Task 6.4), will offer an opportunity to demonstrate how the information products and toolbox produced under the project can support the needs identified in these reports, particularly in reference to MPAs and blue carbon.

2.2 European marine biodiversity legal and policy instruments

European Union level instruments give effect to international commitments at the European level as well as establishing regional priorities and requirements on Member States. To maximize the relevance and impact of the toolbox and information products created under OBAMA-NEXT, it is crucial that they align closely with the data needed for the successful implementation and monitoring of European marine biodiversity policy. The policy data needs review undertaken for this deliverable (see section 4) provides the basis for this. Within this data analysis, the data needs relating to specific, relevant provisions in EU Directives and RSCAPs were used to identify these data needs 'at source'.

¹¹ See also Pörtner, H. O., R. J. Scholes, J. Agard, E. Archer, A. Arneeth, X. Bai, D. Barnes, M. Burrows, L. Chan, W. L. Cheung, S. Diamond, C. Donatti, C. Duarte, N. Eisenhauer, W. Foden, M. A. Gasalla, C. Handa, T. Hickler, O. Hoegh-Guldberg, K. Ichii, U. Jacob, G. Insarov, W. Kiessling, P. Leadley, R. Leemans, L. Levin, M. Lim, S. Maharaj, S. Managi, P. A. Marquet, P. McElwee, G. Midgley, T. Oberdorff, D. Obura, E. Osman, R. Pandit, U. Pascual, A. P. F. Pires, A. Popp, V. ReyesGarcía, M. Sankaran, J. Settele, Y. J. Shin, D. W. Sintayehu, P. Smith, N. Steiner, B. Strassburg, R. Sukumar, C. Trisos, A. L. Val, J. Wu, E. Aldrian, C. Parmesan, R. Pichs-Madruga, D. C. Roberts, A. D. Rogers, S. Díaz, M. Fischer, S. Hashimoto, S. Lavorel, N. Wu, H. T. Ngo, 2021. Scientific outcome of the IPBES-IPCC co-sponsored workshop on biodiversity and climate change (Report). [doi:10.5281/zenodo.4659158](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4659158): 256 pp.

2.2.1 EU marine biodiversity law and policy

Commitments to maintain and improve marine biodiversity are included not only in marine-specific EU policies but form part of high-level regional economic and environmental strategies including the European Green Deal (2019), the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 and the Recovery Plan for Europe (2020)^{12,13} particularly through the articulation of the MSFD as the environmental pillar of the integrated maritime policy. However, European environmental policy, and legislation, including for marine biodiversity, is distributed across a range of instruments (see Annex A).¹⁴ One practical reason for the diversity of instruments is that while the conservation of marine biological resources under the Common Fisheries Policy is an area of exclusive competence for the EU, other aspects of fisheries policy, including aquaculture, as well as environment policy are areas of shared competence, meaning that Member States are able to adopt legally binding acts in these areas, where the EU has not done so. Marine biodiversity at the EU level is regulated through four key pieces of binding legislation:

- The Birds Directive [1979]
- The Habitats Directive [1979] (together with the Birds Directive sometimes known as the Nature Directives¹⁵)
- The Marine Strategy Framework Directive [2008] (MSFD)
- The Water Framework Directive [2000] (WFD)

Due to their central role, these formed the basis of the analysis undertaken for this deliverable, along with the relevant RSCAPs. In addition, the EU Nature Restoration Law is expected to become a crucial pillar of the EU biodiversity law when it is adopted. At the time the analysis of WP6.1 was undertaken, key aspects of the draft legislation were still being actively negotiated and the text has not been included in the current analysis. However, given the significant implications of this law for marine biodiversity it may be important to return to this once the final text has been agreed or is close to final adoption and to feed this into the analysis and other work packages where possible.

The Nature Directives aim to conserve biodiversity through the protection of specified species and habitats, as listed in the Annexes to those Directives. To achieve this, the Habitats Directive specifies (Article 3) that a “coherent European ecological network of special areas of conservation shall be set up under the title Natura 2000”. This network, as established under Article 3, also includes special protected areas as designated under the Birds Directive. The Nature Directives therefore create obligations relating to specific species and habitats but also require spatial measures in the form of protected areas. Marine Protected Areas are therefore a crucial

¹² See [Supplementary Dataset 1](#) for more on the key commitments set out in these policies.

¹³ The Recovery Plan (European Commission, 2021b) for Europe is not itself mapped under this deliverable but - Transforming the EU's Blue Economy for a Sustainable Future (European Commission, 2021a) - sets out an agenda for the sustainable blue economy in the EU with reference both to the Recovery Plan and the Green Deal.

¹⁴ See Article 3 and 4 TFEU (2016/C 202/01)

¹⁵ These are referred to as the 'BHDs' in the OBAMA-NEXT proposal document.

component of the EU marine biodiversity policy in this context and more broadly. The EU MPA network is composed of sites established according to regional and national designation processes that follow specific national policies, often linked to the presence of species and habitats of national and/or regional conservation importance alongside the existing EU frameworks.¹⁶

In looking at the data needs and gaps (see Section 4) it is also important to understand that their purpose corresponds to the aims of the relevant Regulations and the use of cross-cutting concepts that are used to deliver them. These broader concepts are crucial to realising the aims and goals of related legislation and imply data needs beyond listed species and habitats, often including measures related to quality. The concepts are central to realising the applicable legislative objectives and should be understood as underpinning all legislative data needs, though the extent to which those needs are elaborated in the texts is variable. The Habitats Directive, for instance aims for habitats to be maintained or restored to ‘favourable conservation status’ and to achieve ‘ecological coherence’ in the Natura 2000 network. The MSFD aims to achieve ‘good environmental status’, defined as *“ecologically diverse and dynamic oceans and seas which are clean, healthy and productive within their intrinsic conditions, and the use of the marine environment is at a level that is sustainable...”*¹⁷ The MSFD also requires that the network of MPAs created is ‘coherent and representative’ and requires that strategies apply an ‘ecosystem-based approach’.¹⁸ These concepts create data needs based on the corresponding implementation and reporting requirements. Further data needs may relate to other or related requirements such as those for designating sites and adopting plans, strategies and targets and articulated through additional detail in annexes, descriptors and additional guidance. In some cases, these data needs are clearly identified and defined, in others, there is more discretion afforded to Member States in interpreting the concepts and determining how to meet the requirements.¹⁹ Crucially, these underpinning concepts should be kept in mind when understanding the purpose of data in relation to regulatory requirements and the role that potential information products can serve.

The four key legislative instruments pre-date what are now the key regional, European policies and therefore some more recent European policy commitments and approaches are not yet reflected in legislative provisions. The EU is actively developing legislation to implement these commitments, for instance, in the form of the EU Nature Restoration Law, which is currently under development and will put key commitments from the

¹⁶ An important additional set of commitments and measures relate to the sustainable use of the components of biological diversity including in the context of fisheries. While by-catch and fisheries measures have been included in the where they were found in the included reporting formats, a comprehensive review of EU fisheries policy was beyond the scope of this project.

¹⁷ Art 3(5)

¹⁸ Art 3(4). An ecosystems-based approach is also specified under the Common Fisheries Policy: under Article 13 CFP an ecosystem-based approach to fisheries management needs to be implemented, environmental impacts of fishing activities should be limited and unwanted catches should be avoided and reduced as far as possible.

¹⁹ The challenges in defining and implementing GES have been widely recognised including in the 2020 review by the European Commission (2020a)

Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 into practice.²⁰ In the meantime, the detailed data needs that will flow from further developments are not known. Some preliminary comments on the implications of key commitments in relation to data needs are provided in the table in [Supplementary Dataset 1](#).

2.2.2 Regional Seas Programmes

The Regional Seas Programmes support transboundary cooperation on marine policy, including for biodiversity and ecosystems, between neighbouring countries at the sea-basin level. They operate under the framework of an applicable Regional Seas Convention (RSCs) (a legally binding treaty) and regional Action Plan (which may or may not have a legally binding component to its implementation) and are together referred to as RSCAPs.

There are four RSCs relevant to European marine policy, of which the European Commission is a contracting party to all but the Bucharest Convention:

- The Barcelona Convention for the Protection of the Marine Environment and the Coastal Region of the Mediterranean (1995) (UNEP-MAP)
- The Bucharest Convention on the Protection of the Black Sea Against Pollution (1992)
- Helsinki Convention on the Protection of the Marine Environment of the Baltic Sea Area (1992) (HELCOM)
- The Oslo and Paris (OSPAR) Convention for the Protection of the Marine Environment of the North-East Atlantic (1992)

Regional Seas Programmes play a significant role in European marine governance including the implementation of EU marine law and policy and in some cases the EU has named RSCs and in its instruments. In particular, the MSFD requires Contracting Parties to “*use existing regional institutional cooperation structures, including those under Regional Sea Conventions, covering that marine region or subregion*”.²¹ The MSFD also requires that Contracting Parties “take into account” assessments made under RSCs.²² This means that the assessments, indicators and action plans adopted under RSCs can support contracting parties in the implementation of the MSFD. At the same time, RSCs have, in some cases, adopted the concept of “Good Environmental Status” and the contracting parties have assessment and reporting commitments, of varying degrees, related to this under RSCAPs. RSCs also play a role in establishing MPAs. For example, HELCOM guidance on the designation of MPAs permits MPAs designated under Natura 2000 and MSFD sites, to also be recognised as HELCOM sites, but only where the specified HELCOM protection requirements are also met.²³ Similarly, OSPAR and the Barcelona

²⁰ See latest developments at (European Commission) [The EU #NatureRestoration Law \(europa.eu\)](#)

²¹ Art 6

²² Art 8(2)

²³ See HELCOM, Guidelines for Designating Marine and Coastal Baltic Sea Protected Areas (BSPA) and Proposed Protection Categories (2003) available at [HELCOM-MPA-designation-guidelines.pdf](#)

Convention have established their own criteria for MPA designation.²⁴ This interaction and partial overlap between RSCAPS and the MSFD should be kept in mind when reviewing the data needs and gaps identified in section 4 of this report.

²⁴ For the Barcelona Convention see Protocol Concerning Specially Protected Areas and Biological Diversity in the Mediterranean, Annex I Common Criteria for the Choice of Protected Marine and Coastal Areas that could be included in the SPAMI List available at [annex_1_en.pdf \(rac-spa.org\)](#). For the OSPAR Convention see Guidelines for the Identification and Selection of Marine Protected Areas in the OSPAR Maritime Area (OSPAR Agreement: 2003-17) available at [Guidance for the development and management of the OSPAR network | OSPAR Commission](#).

3. Process to identify data needs and gaps in marine biodiversity policy

The methodology to identify data needs in relevant policies followed a 5-step process (Figure 2). First, key policy instruments were identified and refined to create a short-list of eight policy instruments used in the analysis. Then key documents for these target policy instruments were identified. This included the instrument primary text, annexes and reporting templates. Next, the data needs from these documents were extracted and compared to identify data which underpin multiple instruments. Finally, gaps in information required for the eight policy instruments were identified through a review of academic and grey literature. Consultations with the project advisory board (PAB) and consortium members was undertaken throughout the process.

Figure 2. Workflow used to identify data needs and gaps in information in European marine biodiversity policy

3.1 Selection of legal and policy instruments

An iterative approach involving all members of task 6.1 was used to select which legal and policy instruments would be included in the policy data needs analysis. Key legal and policy instruments were identified in the proposal as a starting point (e.g. MSFD, EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030, CBD, UNFCCC) and an initial long-list of forty-three European and international marine biodiversity related legal and policy instruments was compiled (Annex A). This was subsequently narrowed down to a proposed list of eight instruments related directly to the focus of the OBAMA-NEXT work packages. The final list (Annex B) also considered inputs from the consortium partners and policy developments (including the EU action plan on protecting and restoring marine ecosystems for sustainable and resilient fisheries and the Nature Restoration Law) that had taken place during the initial phases of the project. The process for selecting these instruments, and the input provided from partners across the consortium, is explained further below.

Several key legal and policy instruments that outlined international obligations and commitments were included in the project proposal and these were used as a starting point in the list of instruments to be analyzed. From

here, a more comprehensive list of instruments was collated through the mapping of marine legislation and policy across Europe including RSCAPs, EU Directives and international instruments. This list of forty-three instruments was then presented to partners across the project consortium for feedback.

Through consultation with project consortium partners, a revised list of seven instruments was drafted due to the time constraints of the analysis. This included all relevant RSCAPs, the MSFD, and the BHD. These were selected because of their far-ranging applicability, influence and relevance to European marine biodiversity policy. In parallel to this, a survey was distributed amongst the PAB through the activities of WP1. The PAB members identified the MSFD and WFD as the instruments that they needed the greatest assistance with, in terms of reporting. Taking this into consideration and after further co-development with partners, the WFD was added leading to a total of eight key legal and policy instruments for the analysis (Annex B).

3.2 Identification of policy data needs

To identify the data needs of the eight selected instruments an iterative and collaborative approach was used. This approach incorporated feedback from consortium partners and refined the focus and scale of the data needs recorded to ensure the harmonization of the information products developed under the project. Alongside this collaborative process, key methodological steps were followed to ensure the accurate identification of the policy instrument data needs. Within each step of this process, co-development from consortium partners within task 6.1 was sought through meetings and the provision of written feedback.

A review of the text and annexes of each of the selected Directives and RSCAPs was undertaken, including reporting templates and guidelines, European Commission decisions and RSC monitoring programmes to extract the policy instrument data needs (Table 1). From here, data needs from the documents were categorized (see Annex C) to facilitate comparisons between instruments. To categorize the data needs, the MSFD data descriptors (forming 11 categories) were used as they provide a commonly used terminology for referring to types of marine data (Smith *et al.*, 2022) that would enable synchronization/harmonization across the project. In addition to these categories, each data need was categorized by the data type (physical, chemical and biological) and information type (state, pressure and impact) to increase the utility of the information provided for other work packages within the project. Data needs were compiled into a single dataset ([Supplementary Dataset 2](#)). The number of instruments requiring each data need were counted and visualized using R Studio.

Table 1. Documentation used to extract data needs for four Regional Seas Conventions and Action Plans and four Directives.

Instrument	Data needs source
Marine Strategy Framework Directive	Annex I of the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (2008/56/EC; European Commission, 2008) Commission Decision 2017/848/ EU (European Union, 2017a) Commission Decision 2017/845/EU (European Union, 2017b)

	<p>Joint Resource Centre’s (JRC) reference lists of species and habitats (Palialexis et al., 2018).</p> <p>The second workshop on lists of commercial fish and shellfish species for reporting of MSFD D3 (WKD3LISTS2; ICES, 2022)</p>
Habitats Directive	<p>Annex I, II, IV and V of the Habitats Directive (92/43/EEC; European Commission, 1992)</p> <p>Article 17 Reporting Format Parts B, C and D (European Environment Agency, 2022c)</p> <p>Explanatory Notes in support to the reporting format referred to in article 17 of directive 92/43/EEC (European Environment Agency, 2022b)</p> <p>Explanatory Notes & Guidelines for the period 2007-2012 (Evans and Arvela, 2011)</p> <p>List of pressures and threats for the period 2019-2024 version 24/01/23 (European Environment Agency, 2023)</p>
Birds Directive	<p>Article 12 Reporting Format Parts A and B (2019-2024; European Environment Agency)</p> <p>List of pressures and threats for the period 2019-2024 version 24/01/23 (European Environment Agency, 2023)</p> <p>Checklist for bird species version 09/11/2021 (European Environment Agency, 2021)</p>
Water Framework Directive	<p>Sections 1.1.3 and 1.1.4 of Annex V of the Water Framework Directive (2000/60/EC; European Commission, 2000)</p>
OSPAR Convention	<p>OSPAR Coordinated Environmental Monitoring Programme (CEMP) including Guidelines & appendices (OSPAR Commission, 2016)</p>
Barcelona Convention	<p>Decision IG.22/7 in Integrated Monitoring and Assessment Programme of the Mediterranean Sea and Coast (UN Environment/MAP, 2017)</p>
Bucharest Convention	<p>Black Sea Integrated Monitoring and Assessment Programme for years 2017-2022 (BSIMAP, 2017)</p> <p>‘Diagnostic Report’ to guide improvements to the regular reporting process on the state of the Black Sea environment (Commission on the Protection of the Black Sea Against Pollution, 2010)</p>
Helsinki Convention	<p>HELCOM Monitoring Manual including monitoring programmes (HELCOM)</p>

Once the data needs had been extracted, the relevant species and habitats lists of the instruments were identified using the documentation listed in Table 1. An outline of this workflow process is shown in Figure 3. Marine species listed in the BHD were identified as those recorded in the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as marine or brackish. The worrms R Package was used to search species names in WoRMS (Chamberlain and Vanhoorne, 2023). For the other marine-focused instruments, all species listed were included in the analysis. Habitat types were too complex to compare between instruments as standardized habitat classifications (e.g. European Nature Information System - EUNIS) were not consistently used across instruments. A crosswalk was used to convert habitat types listed in Annex I of the Habitats Directive to the standardized EUNIS habitat types (European Environment Agency, 2022a). Lists of species and habitats for each instrument were compiled into single species ([Supplementary Dataset 3](#)) and habitat ([Supplementary Dataset 4](#)) datasets and further categorized by ecosystem components to facilitate comparisons between instruments. Ecosystem components are defined as constituents of an ecosystem or marine waters and include taxa groups such as birds and mammals and parts of the marine environment such as benthic and pelagic habitats (Smith *et al.*, 2022).

Figure 3. Example of the process for identifying data needs from specific sources for some of the target instruments.

3.3 Identification of gaps in information required in law and policy

To identify the gaps in information required by the selected legal and policy instruments, a literature review was performed. Academic literature was reviewed relating to the eight marine policy instruments identified. The review of academic literature was conducted through Google Scholar and used 16 keywords to search for information gaps across the eight policy instruments (Annex D). Keyword searches for academic journal articles relating to the MSFD, BHD and WFD were restricted after 2018 to ensure that only gaps belonging to the last reporting period were identified. Google scholar keyword searches for policy instruments relating to the RSCAPs were also restricted to 2018. A total of sixteen journal articles (see [Supplementary Dataset 5](#)) were found to include relevant gaps in information required within the legal and policy instruments analysed.

The review of grey literature primarily consisted of using keyword searches to identify official reports, such as implementation reports, fitness checks and status reports relating to the eight policy instruments. An initial search using Google was undertaken using keyword searches (Annex D) to identify and analyse relevant reports. This was followed by a second round of searches using the same keywords on the official websites of the EU and the different RSCAPs websites to help identify further relevant grey literature (see Annex D for websites used). A total of nineteen sources (see [Supplementary Dataset 5](#)) were found to include relevant gaps in information required within the policy instruments analysed. The gaps in information identified were compiled into a single dataset (see [Supplementary Dataset 5](#)). Each gap in information was categorized by the MSFD descriptor and data need using the same criteria that was used to categorize the data needs (Annex C). Where information was available, details on the species, habitat, region or location and time period were also recorded.

3.4 Limitations of methodology

The scope of this deliverable posed a limit on the amount of literature that could be reviewed. Moreover, grey literature, such as implementation reports, were difficult to identify through keyword searches. Due to this, the majority of the grey literature reviewed originated from the websites of the EU and the RSCAPs. Independent reports that were not located in the keyword searches may have been omitted.

The focus on the type of information gaps in policy also provided a limitation to the research. The data needs recorded focused on marine biodiversity without incorporating a full range of direct and indirect drivers such as fisheries, social or economic dimensions. For instance, data needs relating to activities such as fishing effort or employment in the fishing industry, or specific conservation measures and land use changes, were not included as they were not the focus of the information products to be developed under the OBAMA-NEXT project. In this sense, the focus on positivist natural science data related to reporting was prioritized over more sectoral, socio-economic and qualitative data that affects policy effectiveness and implementation. This meant that the analyzed literature focussed on state-pressure-impact information relating to policy implementation, rather than policy effectiveness or enforcement. In addition, this narrower scope of analysis did not include information relating to indigenous and local knowledge systems or alternative ways of knowing and valuing the marine environment.

4. Data needs and gaps in information required for European marine biodiversity policy

4.1 Data needs required for European marine biodiversity policy

The data that Member States are required to report on were identified for eight relevant European policy instruments. Those that were required for reporting on multiple instruments, hereafter referred to as “multiple instrument data needs”. These can have greater value when considering the development of information products within OBAMA-NEXT, as a single dataset can be more effective and of higher value by contributing to multiple instruments. Data needs were categorized by the eleven MSFD descriptors: Biodiversity, Non-indigenous species, Commercially exploited fish and shellfish, Marine food webs, Eutrophication, Seafloor integrity, Hydrological conditions, Contaminants, Contaminants in fish and other seafood, Marine litter and Underwater noise and other forms of energy. Data needs can encompass a variety of metrics (detailed in the Annex C). For example, the population demographics data need within the Biodiversity descriptor includes data on abundance, age and size distribution, sex ratio, reproductive indicators (e.g. fecundity), mortality rate, survival rate and nutritional status. Priority was given in the analysis to data needs in the Biodiversity and Seafloor integrity descriptors, in line with the focus of WP2 (pelagic habitats), WP3 (benthic habitats) and WP4 (toolbox for biodiversity, habitats and ecosystem function) to be developed under OBAMA-NEXT.

Species and habitats that Member States are required to report on were categorized by ecosystem components to aid the identification of taxa groups and components of the marine environment required for reporting for multiple instruments. Ecosystem components for species were those specified in Smith *et al.* (2022); birds, mammals, reptiles, fish, and cephalopods, as well as macroalgae, benthic invertebrates, zooplankton and plants, as these were required for reporting by instruments other than the MSFD. Ecosystem components for habitats were categorized as either benthic or pelagic and the broad habitat types specified in Smith *et al.* (2022) were used to identify habitats required for reporting for multiple instruments.

4.1.1 Biodiversity

Data on species distribution and population demographics were identified as multiple instrument data needs within the Biodiversity descriptor as both were required for reporting on seven out of the eight instruments analysed (Figure 4; [Supplementary Dataset 2](#)). Species distribution referred to the distribution or range of listed species. Under the population demographics descriptor category, several of the metrics were required for multiple instruments with abundance being the most common (seven instruments) followed by age and size distribution, and reproductive indicators (four instruments). Community composition of phytoplankton and zooplankton, macrophytes and macrofauna and bycatch of vulnerable and non-target species such as mammals, reptiles, seabirds and non-commercially exploited fish and cephalopods were required for reporting on five instruments.

Population demographics and species distribution data were required for marine mammals in five out of eight instruments, and for seabirds in five (population demographics) and four (species distribution) out of eight instruments (Figure 5). Data for benthic invertebrates (e.g. crustaceans, echinoderms, cnidarians and molluscs) were required in four instruments, fish in four (population demographics) and three (species distribution) instruments and reptiles (marine turtles) and plants in three instruments. Long-term (24 years) and short-term (12 years) changes in population demographics and species distribution were required in the BHD only. These findings are in line with the results of the PAB survey undertaken in WP1 where PAB members identified a need for data on the spatial and temporal distribution of species and habitats.

Figure 4. Data needs required for reporting for European marine biodiversity related Directives and Regional Sea Conventions categorized by the Biodiversity descriptor from Marine Strategy Framework Directive

Ecosystem component categories were useful in the comparison of high-level data needs, but species lists differed greatly between instruments ([Supplementary Dataset 3 and 4](#)). For example, data on population demographics and species distribution were required for a total of forty-two unique mammal species across five instruments. But none of these individual species were required in all five instruments although data on ten of these forty-two species were required across four instruments. This was also the case for the other ecosystem components, likely reflecting differing species occurrence between the regional seas. For example, few mammal species are present in the Black Sea, in comparison to the NE Atlantic, resulting in few species to be reported on for the Bucharest Convention (3 species) compared to the OSPAR Convention (24 species). The information products developed under the OBAMA-NEXT project could prioritize the species that are required for multiple policy instruments. However, this approach would then prioritise species with the largest geographic ranges as they are required in multiple RSCAPs, and potentially would neglect more localized species of conservation concern such as the endangered Mediterranean monk seal (*Monachus monachus*).

Habitat distribution and change in habitat distribution data was required in four instruments (for biogenic benthic habitats) and two instruments (for pelagic habitats). The biogenic benthic habitat types required for reporting against the highest number of instruments were infralittoral rock and biogenic reef (e.g. kelp forests and oyster beds; [Supplementary Dataset 4](#)). This was the only broad habitat type that was identified across the four instruments that required habitat distribution data. Deep sea habitats such as abyssal and bathyal rock and biogenic reef (e.g. deep sea corals and communities associated with seamounts) were required in three instruments, as were shallower littoral (e.g. coastal vegetation) and circalittoral (e.g. coralligenous habitats and mussel beds) rock and biogenic reef.

Figure 5. Biodiversity data needs required for reporting for European marine biodiversity-related Directives and Regional Sea Conventions and Action Plans for different ecosystem components for population demographics/change in population demographics, species distribution/change in species distribution and habitat distribution/change in habitat distribution data.

4.1.2 Seafloor integrity

Within the Seafloor integrity descriptor, benthic habitat distribution and change in habitat distribution data for non-biogenic habitats were required in four instruments (Figure 6). The non-biogenic benthic habitats required for reporting against the most instruments were infralittoral coarse and mixed sediment, mud and sand (e.g. sandbanks, estuaries, coastal lagoons and shallow inlets and bays; [Supplementary Dataset 4](#)). These data were identified across four of the instruments that required habitat distribution data. Abyssal habitats and bathyal rock (e.g. reefs, seamounts and hydrothermal vents) and circalittoral coarse and mixed sediment, mud, rock and sand were required for three instruments. Seafloor structure data (e.g. bathymetry and substrate type) were required in three instruments and the MSFD required data on seafloor disturbance, specifically the extent of the assessment area physically lost or disturbed per broad habitat type, implying that mapping the distribution and extent of these habitats was essential.

Figure 6. Data needs required for reporting for European marine biodiversity related Directives and Regional Sea Conventions and Action Plans categorized by the Seafloor integrity Marine Strategy Framework Directive descriptor.

4.1.3 Other descriptors

Other multiple instrument data needs included, nutrient concentration (Eutrophication descriptor) and contaminant concentration (Contaminants descriptor), which were required for reporting against five out of eight instruments ([Supplementary Dataset 2](#) and Annex E). There were twelve data needs that were only required by one instrument and therefore may be considered a lower priority when developing information products within the OBAMA-NEXT project.

Other data not within the Biodiversity descriptor category required at the species level included fisheries catch, fishing impacts and population demographics of commercial species (Commercially important fish and shellfish

descriptor). These were required in three instruments, and litter in biota (Marine litter descriptor) which was required for three reptile species (OSPAR Convention).

Despite the identification of data needs for different species and habitats across the eight instruments analyzed, other factors can limit coordinated monitoring efforts. These include different spatial and temporal scales and different reporting schedules between instruments (Franco *et al.*, 2021). For example, short-term or local scale monitoring that is suitable for some instruments will not meet the reporting requirements for other instruments that require longer time series or broad spatial scale data. In addition, reporting should be based on the most recent data, and mismatches in reporting cycles can then prevent data from one assessment period being used for reporting on multiple instruments. Where possible, developing standardized national monitoring efforts for species listed in multiple instruments can avoid data collection being duplicated and help optimize resources. For example, data on species distribution and population demographics of *Pinna nobilis*, *Patella ferruginea* and *Tursiops truncatus* in Mediterranean EU Member States will contribute to reporting requirements for both the HD and MSFD (La Mesa *et al.*, 2021). This kind of coordinated monitoring may be more easily applied to species than habitats due to differences in the classification of habitats, for example between the HD and MSFD, which can limit the integration of assessments for habitats (Franco *et al.*, 2021).

4.2 Gaps in information required for European marine biodiversity policy

Gaps in the information required for relevant European policy instruments were identified through a literature review and include general gaps in data needs (e.g., species distribution data) as well as more specific gaps for particular species (e.g. *Tursiops truncatus*), habitats (e.g. deep sea), regions (e.g. Black Sea) and time periods (e.g. historical data). The gaps described in the following section provide an indication of where data is not available and may be filled by information products produced under OBAMA-NEXT.

Gaps in information were identified for all eleven descriptors, all ecosystem components (except macroalgae) and all four regions ([Supplementary Dataset 5](#)). There were gaps in information identified for two descriptors for seabirds and reptiles (Biodiversity and Marine litter) and fish (Biodiversity and Marine food webs) and the Biodiversity descriptor only for mammals, benthic invertebrates, cephalopods and plants. There were gaps in information identified for biogenic benthic and pelagic habitats for the Biodiversity descriptor and non-biogenic benthic habitats for the Seafloor integrity descriptor. Data gaps were identified for all eleven descriptors for the Mediterranean Sea, ten descriptors for the Black Sea, nine descriptors for the North-East Atlantic and eight descriptors for the Baltic Sea. Lack of time series data was identified for five descriptors and baseline or historical data for three descriptors.

While this analysis indicates where efforts are required to fill gaps in information, biases were identified in the results. This was because there was more literature available and therefore more gaps identified for the most studied species, habitats and regions. For example, more gaps were identified for the Mediterranean Sea

compared to other regions. However, previous reviews have indicated that much of the available data collected to date are for the North-East Atlantic, Mediterranean Sea and Baltic Sea with the Black Sea being the most data deficient (Dailianis *et al.*, 2018; Gerovasileiou *et al.*, 2019).

4.2.1 Biodiversity

Species distribution (e.g. range and suitable habitat area and condition) and population demographics (e.g. abundance and mortality rate) of seabirds, mammals (cetaceans and pinnipeds), reptiles (turtles), fish and cephalopods were identified as gaps in information (European Commission, 2020a; Franco *et al.*, 2021; Tornero Alvarez *et al.*, 2023), despite also being identified in this analysis as multiple instrument data needs. Despite some improvements from 2015, poor and incomplete species range and population size data sets have remained an issue in the 2013-2018 reporting period for the BHD with much of the reported information coming from partial surveys and expert opinion (European Commission, 2020b). In addition, species distribution, including habitat for species and breeding distribution, and population demographics, including abundance and mortality rate, were identified as gaps in reports for the MSFD (Franco *et al.*, 2018; Tornero Alvarez *et al.*, 2023), OSPAR Convention (Banga *et al.*, 2022; Geelhoed *et al.*, 2022) and Barcelona Convention (UNEP, 2018).

The 2013-2018 State of Nature Report (European Commission, 2020b) found a greater number of gaps in reporting against the BHD for species than for habitats, and a greater number of marine species (59%) had an “unknown” status compared to terrestrial species (8%). The report identified insufficient available resources for monitoring as the cause for the gaps. In this analysis, gaps in information for individual species were most frequently identified for marine mammals (*Delphinus delphis* and *Tursiops truncatus*) and marine turtles (*Caretta caretta* and *Chelonia mydas*). All of these species were required for reporting against multiple instruments. A more detailed assessment of just the Habitats Directive identified gaps in information for twenty-seven species including fourteen mammal species, five reptile species, six benthic invertebrate species and two plant species (La Mesa *et al.*, 2021). The prevalence of gaps in information for marine mammals and reptiles may be due to the highly mobile and migratory nature of these taxa, which often require resource-intensive monitoring efforts and cooperation between Member States (Franco *et al.*, 2021; La Mesa *et al.*, 2021; Geelhoed *et al.*, 2022). For example, gaps in information were identified for *Monachus monachus*, where data are currently based on validated sightings, due to the resource intensive broad scale monitoring efforts required as result of the species’ cryptic habitat use and low density (La Mesa *et al.*, 2021). In addition, gaps in abundance estimates for low-density species with variable detection rates such as *Delphinus delphis* were identified (Murphy *et al.*, 2021).

Temporal trends in species distribution and population demographics required for the BHD were identified as gaps in information as regional and national scale surveys are often not undertaken with the regularity required to assess trends. For example, broad-scale surveys of cetacean abundance and distribution in the North-East Atlantic have been infrequent (only undertaken in 1994, 2005, 2007 and 2016) resulting in a time series too short for assessing species’ status (Geelhoed *et al.*, 2022). In addition, a lack of time series data on species range,

habitat for species and population size was identified for a range of ecosystem components at the national scale (La Mesa *et al.*, 2021). Assessment of trends requires longevity in monitoring programmes and standardized methodologies that allow comparisons between years. While annual surveys need to be carried out in the same season to accurately assess the impact of human pressures on species in the absence of seasonal variability (La Mesa *et al.*, 2021), surveys carried out in a single season result in gaps in information on seasonal variations (Geelhoed *et al.*, 2022). For example, there was a lack of data on seasonal variation in cetacean distribution and abundance as surveys were often conducted in summer for logistical reasons (Geelhoed *et al.*, 2022).

Gaps in habitat distribution including habitat condition and change in habitat distribution data were identified for seagrass habitats (Traganos and Reinartz, 2018) and open waters (Varkitzi *et al.*, 2018). Regional scale maps of seagrass species distribution are being developed improving previously patchy maps, however, they have limited applicability to deeper waters (Traganos *et al.*, 2022). Patchy spatial coverage of habitat data has also been identified for pelagic habitats (Magliozzi *et al.*, 2021), as data sets on the use of plankton as indicators of habitat condition have often been limited to shallow coastal waters (Varkitzi *et al.*, 2018). Monitoring of plankton communities is difficult due to the large number of species that comprise communities and high temporal and spatial variability in assemblages, making it difficult to summarize information and identify changes due to human pressures (Varkitzi *et al.*, 2018).

4.2.2 Seafloor integrity

Data gaps were identified regarding habitat distribution and change in habitat distribution required to report against four instruments. This included data relating to non-biogenic benthic habitats such as shallow hard substrates and deep-sea habitats. Shallow hard substrates are often mapped using small-scale surveying methodologies (e.g. SCUBA), resulting in patchy spatial coverage (Gerovasileiou *et al.*, 2019). In addition, data collection and mapping of deep-sea habitats is hampered by its inaccessibility often requiring resource-intensive monitoring efforts (Franco *et al.*, 2021; La Mesa *et al.*, 2021; Geelhoed *et al.*, 2022), though efforts have increased in recent years to fill data gaps (Gerovasileiou *et al.*, 2019; Danovaro *et al.*, 2020). To date, most data have been obtained through trawling of soft bottom habitats and sampling by remotely operated vehicles of cold-water coral habitats and coral gardens (Danovaro *et al.*, 2020).

Seafloor disturbance data, such as habitat loss and degradation required for reporting for the MSFD, were also identified as a gap in information (Crise *et al.*, 2015; Dailianis *et al.*, 2018; Gerovasileiou *et al.*, 2019). These gaps may result from a lack of baseline data and harmonized methodologies making it difficult to determine the current status of habitats (Gerovasileiou *et al.*, 2019). Long-term time series and understanding of natural variability are required to establish baseline habitat condition and determine thresholds for defining habitat status but these are costly to collect (e.g., Good Environmental Status; Varkitzi *et al.*, 2018).

4.2.3 Other descriptors

Other multiple instrument data needs that were identified as information gaps included nutrient concentration (Eutrophication) and contaminant concentration (Contaminants). Although, monitoring programmes associated with the WFD and RSCAPs have resulted in extensive eutrophication and contaminant datasets across Member States, there was still a lack of offshore data for nutrient concentration, phytoplankton indicators, concentrations of specific contaminants and long-term time series data for coastal chlorophyll-a in Southern Europe (Crise *et al.*, 2015; UNEP, 2018). In addition, there has been uncertainty in nutrient input from atmospheric and land-based sources in the Baltic Sea due to the limited modelling of biogeochemical cycles (Climate Change in the Baltic Sea, 2021). The only non-Biodiversity-related gaps in information that were identified on an individual species level were gaps in litter impacts (Marine litter) on *Caretta caretta* and *Fulmaris glacialis* (Galgani *et al.*, 2022; Kühn *et al.*, 2022).

5. Conclusion

Insufficient, incoherent and missing information on marine species, habitats, ecosystems and anthropogenic pressures hampers the ability to evaluate the effectiveness of management actions and policy instruments. Understanding the data needs of policy instruments is a required first step in this project in developing the information products needed to fill the gaps and support evidence-based decision making and relevant policies. Species distribution and population demographics data were some of the data needs identified in this deliverable that underpinned multiple instruments as well as where there were gaps, and as such should be a focus of data collection, generation, compilation and synthesis. This report provides the foundation and guidance for the future development of information products under OBAMA-NEXT, to ensure that the products can support the effective management of marine ecosystems and the services they provide.

6. References

2016/C 202/01 (2016) *Consolidated versions of the Treaty on European Union and the Treaty on the functioning of the European Union*, Official Journal of the European Union, pp. 47–360. Available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A12016ME%2FTXT> (Accessed: 13 September 2023).

Agnesi, S., Annunziatellis, A., Chaniotis, P., Mo, G., Korpinen, S., Snoj, L., Tunesi, L., Reker, J., 2020, *Spatial Analysis of Marine Protected Area Networks in Europe's Seas III*. ETC/ ICM Technical Report 3/2020: European Topic Centre on Inland, Coastal and Marine waters, 40. Available at: <https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-icm/products/etc-icm-reports/etc-icm-report-3-2020-spatial-analysis-of-marine-protected-area-networks-in-europe2019s-seas-iii> (Accessed: 25 October 2023).

Banga, R. *et al.* (2022) *Seal Abundance and Distribution, OSPAR, 2023: The 2023 Quality Status Report for the Northeast Atlantic*. Available at: <https://oap.ospar.org/en/ospar-assessments/quality-status-reports/qs-2023/indicator-assessments/seal-abundance-and-distribution> (Accessed: 7 September 2023).

Barcelona Convention, Protocol Concerning Specially Protected Areas and Biological Diversity in the Mediterranean, Annex I Common Criteria for the Choice of Protected Marine and Coastal Areas that could be included in the SPAMI List available at [annex_1_en.pdf \(rac-spa.org\)](http://www.rac-spa.org/annex_1_en.pdf).

Bindoff, N. L. *et al.* (2019). Changing Ocean, Marine Ecosystems, and Dependent Communities. In *IPCC Special Report on the Ocean and Cryosphere in a Changing Climate*. H.-O. Pörtner *et al.* (Eds.), (pp. 447–588). Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, UK and New York, NY, USA. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781009157964.007>

BSIMAP (2017) *Black Sea Integrated Monitoring and Assessment Program for years 2017-2022 (BSIMAP 2017-2022)*. Available at: <https://www.cbd.int/doc/meetings/mar/ebsaws-2017-01/other/ebsaws-2017-01-bsc-submission-07-en.pdf> (Accessed: 9 October 2023).

Chamberlain, S. and Vanhoorne, B. (2023) *World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) Client. Version 0.4.3*.

Climate Change in the Baltic Sea (2021) *Fact Sheet. Baltic Sea Environment Proceedings n°180*. Available at: <https://helcom.fi/wp-content/uploads/2021/09/Baltic-Sea-Climate-Change-Fact-Sheet-2021.pdf> (Accessed: 14 September 2023).

Commission on the Protection of the Black Sea Against Pollution (2010) *'Diagnostic Report' to guide improvements to the regular reporting process on the state of the Black Sea environment*. Available at: <http://www.blacksea-commission.org/publ-bsdidiagnosticreport2010.asp#:~:text=The%20'Diagnostic%20Report'%20project%20aims,commitments%2C%20stipulated%20in%20BS%20legal%2F> (Accessed: 9 October 2023).

Crise, A. *et al.* (2015) 'A MSFD complementary approach for the assessment of pressures, knowledge and data gaps in Southern European Seas: The PERSEUS experience', *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, 95(1), pp. 28–39. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2015.03.024>.

Dailianis, T. *et al.* (2018) 'Human activities and resultant pressures on key European marine habitats: An analysis of mapped resources', *Marine Policy*, 98, pp. 1–10. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2018.08.038>.

Danovaro, R. *et al.* (2020) 'Towards a marine strategy for the deep Mediterranean Sea: Analysis of current ecological status', *Marine Policy*, 112. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2019.103781>.

European Commission (1992) *Council Directive 92/43/EEC of 21 May 1992 on the conservation of natural habitats and of wild fauna and flora*. Available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:01992L0043-20130701> (Accessed: 9 October 2023).

European Commission (2000) *Directive 2000/60/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 October 2000 establishing a framework for Community action in the field of water policy*. Available at: https://eur-lex.europa.eu/resource.html?uri=cellar:5c835afb-2ec6-4577-bdf8-756d3d694eeb.0004.02/DOC_1&format=PDF (Accessed: 9 October 2023).

European Commission (2008) *Directive 2008/56/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 June 2008 establishing a framework for community action in the field of marine environmental policy (Marine Strategy Framework Directive)*. Available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32008L0056> (Accessed: 9 October 2023).

European Commission (2020a) *Report from the Commission to the European parliament and the Council on the implementation of the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (Directive 2008/56/EC)*. COM/2020/259. Available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52020DC0259> (Accessed: 13/10/2023).

European Commission (2020b) *The state of nature in the European Union: Report on the status and trends in 2013-2018 of species and habitat types protected by the Birds and Habitats Directives*. COM/2020/635. Available at: <https://www.eea.europa.eu/publications/state-of-nature-in-the-eu-2020> (Accessed: 13/10/2023).

European Commission (2021a) *Communication from the Commission to the European parliament, the council, the European economic and social committee and the committee of the regions on a new approach for a sustainable blue economy in the EU Transforming the EU's Blue Economy for a Sustainable Future*. COM/2021/240. Available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52021DC0240> (Accessed: 13/10/2023).

European Commission (2021b) *Putting the Blue into the Green - Sustainable Blue Economy*. Available at: https://oceans-and-fisheries.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2021-05/2021-05-17-sustainable-blue-economy-factsheet_en.pdf (Accessed: 13 September 2023).

European Commission (2022) *MSFD CIS Guidance Document No. 19, Article 8 MSFD, May 2022*. Available at: [https://circabc.europa.eu/d/d/workspace/SpacesStore/d2292fb4-ec39-4123-9a02-2e39a9be37e7/GD19%20-%20MSFDguidance_2022_Art.8Assessment\(1\).pdf](https://circabc.europa.eu/d/d/workspace/SpacesStore/d2292fb4-ec39-4123-9a02-2e39a9be37e7/GD19%20-%20MSFDguidance_2022_Art.8Assessment(1).pdf) (Accessed: 13/10/2023).

European Commission (no date) *Nature restoration law*. Available at: https://environment.ec.europa.eu/topics/nature-and-biodiversity/nature-restoration-law_en (Accessed: 13 September 2023).

European Environment Agency (2021) *Checklist for Bird Species*. Available at: https://cdr.eionet.europa.eu/help/birds_art12/Reporting%202025/Art12%20checklist%2020230630.xlsx (Accessed: 9 October 2023).

European Environment Agency (2022a) *EUNIS marine habitats classification 2022 with crosswalks to Annex I in separate rows*. Available at: <https://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/data/eunis-habitat-classification-1/eunis-marine-habitat-classification-review-2022/eunis-marine-habitats-classification-2022> (Accessed: 8 September 2023).

European Environment Agency (2022b) *Explanatory notes in support to the reporting format referred to in Article 17 of Directive 92/43/EEC (Habitats Directive)*. Available at: https://cdr.eionet.europa.eu/help/habitats_art17/Reporting2025/Explanatory%20notes%20Art%2017%20final.pdf (Accessed: 9 October 2023).

European Environment Agency (2022c) *Reporting format referred to in Article 17 of Directive 92/43/EEC (Habitats Directive)*. Available at: https://cdr.eionet.europa.eu/help/habitats_art17/Reporting2025/Art.17%20report%20format%202019-2024.pdf/ (Accessed: 9 October 2023).

European Environment Agency (2023) *List of pressures and threats for the period 2019-2024*. Available at: https://cdr.eionet.europa.eu/help/habitats_art17/Reporting2025/List%20of%20pressures%20and%20threats%20for%20reporting%202019-2024%20v1.1.xlsx (Accessed: 9 October 2023).

European Environment Agency *Reporting format as referred to in Article 12 of Directive 2009/147/EC (Birds Directive)*. Available at: https://cdr.eionet.europa.eu/help/birds_art12/Reporting%202025/Art.12%20report%20format%202019-2024.pdf (Accessed: 9 October 2023).

European Union (2017a) *Commission Decision (EU) 2017/848 of 17 May 2017 laying down criteria and methodological standards on good environmental status of marine waters and specifications and standardised methods for monitoring and assessment and repealing Decision 2010/477/EU*. Available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32017D0848> (Accessed: 9 October 2023).

European Union (2017b) *Commission Directive (EU) 2017/845 of 17 May 2017 amending Directive 2008/56/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council as regards the indicative lists of elements to be taken into account for the preparation of marine strategies*. Available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32017L0845> (Accessed: 12 October 2023).

Evans, D. and Arvela, M. (2011) *Assessment and reporting under Article 17 of the Habitats Directive: Explanatory Notes & Guidelines for the period 2007-2012*. Available at: <https://circabc.europa.eu/sd/a/2c12cea2-f827-4bdb-bb56-3731c9fd8b40/Art17-Guidelines-final.pdf> (Accessed: 13/10/2023).

Franco, A. et al. (2021) *Coordinated assessments of marine species and habitats under the Birds and Habitats Directives and the Marine Strategy Framework Directive: Process and Technical Review: Main Report (Final)*. IC, MRAG and University of Hull for Directorate General for Environment, European Commission: 202 pp + Annexes.

Galgani, F. et al. (2022) *Marine Litter ingested by Sea Turtles, OSPAR, 2023: The 2023 Quality Status Report for the North-East Atlantic*. Available at: <https://oap.ospar.org/en/ospar-assessments/quality-status-reports/qsr-2023/indicator-assessments/litter-sea-turtles/> (Accessed: 7 September 2023).

Galil, B.S. et al. (2018) 'East is east and West is west? Management of marine bioinvasions in the Mediterranean Sea', *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science*, 201, pp. 7–16. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecss.2015.12.021>.

Geelhoed, S.C.V. et al. (2022) *Abundance and Distribution of Cetaceans, OSPAR, 2023: The 2023 Quality Status Report for the Northeast Atlantic*. Available at: <https://oap.ospar.org/en/ospar-assessments/quality-status-reports/qsr-2023/indicator-assessments/abundance-distribution-cetaceans/> (Accessed: 7 September 2023).

Gerovasileiou, V. et al. (2019) 'Habitat mapping in the European Seas - is it fit for purpose in the marine restoration agenda?', *Marine Policy*, 106. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2019.103521>.

HELCOM Guidelines for Designating Marine and Coastal Baltic Sea Protected Areas (BSPA) and Proposed Protection Categories (2003) available at [HELCOM-MPA-designation-guidelines.pdf](https://www.helcom.fi/wp-content/uploads/2020/10/Introduction-to-the-HELCOM-Monitoring-Manual.pdf)

HELCOM Monitoring Manual. Available at: <https://helcom.fi/wp-content/uploads/2020/10/Introduction-to-the-HELCOM-Monitoring-Manual.pdf> (Accessed: 9 October 2023).

ICES (2022) 'The second workshop on lists of commercial fish and shellfish species for reporting of MSFD D3 (WKD3LISTS2)', ICES SCIENTIFIC REPORTS, 4(80). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.17895/ices.pub.21318255>.

IPBES (2019) *Global assessment report on biodiversity and ecosystem services of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services*. Edited by E.S. Brondizio et al. Bonn, Germany: IPBES secretariat. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3831673> (Accessed: 13 September 2023).

Kühn, S. *et al.* (2022) *Plastic Particles in Fulmar Stomachs in the North Sea, OSPAR, 2023: The 2023 Quality Status Report for the Northeast Atlantic*. Available at: <https://oap.ospar.org/en/ospar-assessments/quality-status-reports/qsr-2023/indicator-assessments/plastic-in-fulmar/> (Accessed: 7 September 2023).

Magliozzi, C. *et al.* (2021) *Pelagic habitats under the MSFD D1: scientific advice of policy relevance, EUR 30671 EN, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, ISBN 978-92-76-35958-6*. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2760/081368,JRC124882>.

La Mesa, G. *et al.* (2021) 'Assessment of the conservation status of marine species of the Habitats Directive (92/43/EEC) in Italy: results, drawbacks and perspectives of the fourth national report (2013–2018)', *Biodiversity and Conservation*, 30(14), pp. 4251–4264. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10531-021-02303-7>.

Murphy, S. *et al.* (2021) 'Conservation management of common dolphins: Lessons learned from the North-East Atlantic', *Aquatic Conservation: Marine and Freshwater Ecosystems*, 31(S1), pp. 137–166. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1002/aqc.3212>.

Ocean & Climate Platform (2023) *What Ocean for Tomorrow? Marine Ecosystems in a Changing Climate, Insights from the IPCC's Sixth Assessment Report*. Available at [DIFCO-2023-EN-web-1.pdf \(ocean-climate.org\)](https://www.ocean-climate.org/DIFCO-2023-EN-web-1.pdf)

OSPAR Commission (2003) Guidelines for the Identification and Selection of Marine Protected Areas in the OSPAR Maritime Area, (OSPAR Agreement: 2003-17) available at [Guidance for the development and management of the OSPAR network | OSPAR Commission](https://www.ospar.org/management-of-the-OSPAR-network).

OSPAR Commission (2016) *OSPAR Coordinated Environmental Monitoring Programme (CEMP)*. Available at: <https://www.ospar.org/documents?v=32943> (Accessed: 9 October 2023).

OSPAR Commission *OSPAR Coordinated Environmental Monitoring Programme (CEMP): Biodiversity and Ecosystems CEMP Guidelines*. Available at: <https://www.ospar.org/work-areas/cross-cutting-issues/cemp> (Accessed: 9 October 2023).

Palialexis, A. *et al.* (2018) *JRC's reference lists of MSFD species and habitats: MSFD reporting for descriptors 1 and 6*. EUR 29125 EN. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2760/794186> (Accessed: 13/10/2023).

Rowe, O. *et al.* (2016) *Underwater noise, Non-indigenous species State of the Baltic Sea Third HELCOM holistic assessment*. Available at: https://helcom.fi/post_type_publ/holas3_haz (Accessed: 14 September 2023).

Smith, C. *et al.* (2022) *Marine Strategy Framework Directive Terminology Definitions and Lists*. GES4SEAS Project, 29 pp. Available at: https://www.ges4seas.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/11/GES4SEAS_Report-Definitions-and-Lists-17112022final.pdf (Accessed: 13/10/2023).

Traganos, D. *et al.* (2022) 'Spatially Explicit Seagrass Extent Mapping Across the Entire Mediterranean', *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 9. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2022.871799>.

Traganos, D. and Reinartz, P. (2018) 'Mapping Mediterranean seagrasses with Sentinel-2 imagery', *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, 134, pp. 197–209. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2017.06.075>.

UNEP (2018) *Executive Summary - 2017 Mediterranean Quality Status Report*. Available at: <https://www.unep.org/unepmap/resources/quality-status-report-mediterranean-med-qsr-2017> (Accessed: 14 September 2023).

UNEP/MAP (2017) *Integrated Monitoring and Assessment Programme of the Mediterranean Sea and Coast and Related Assessment Criteria*. Athens, Greece. Available at: https://wedocs.unep.org/bitstream/handle/20.500.11822/17012/imap_2017_eng.pdf?sequence=5&isAllowed=y#:~:text=their%20sustainable%20development,-

[The%20Integrated%20Monitoring%20and%20Assessment%20Programme%20of%20the%20Mediterranean%20Sea,the%20UN%20Environment%2FMAP%20Barcelona](#) (Accessed: 9 October 2023).

Varkitzi, I. *et al.* (2018) 'Pelagic habitats in the Mediterranean Sea: A review of Good Environmental Status (GES) determination for plankton components and identification of gaps and priority needs to improve coherence for the MSFD implementation', *Ecological Indicators*. Elsevier B.V., pp. 203–218. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2018.07.036>.

7. Annexes

7.1 Annex A - Initial long-list of marine biodiversity related legal and policy instruments identified for analysis

Instrument	Instrument type
High Seas Treaty	International treaty
Barcelona Convention (RSC)	International treaty
Bucharest Convention (RSC)	International treaty
Convention on Biological Diversity	International treaty
Helsinki Convention (RSC)	International treaty
OSPAR Convention (RSC)	International treaty
RAMSAR Convention	International treaty
UN Framework Convention on Climate Change	International treaty
UN Plastics Treaty (under negotiation)	International treaty
Agreement to prevent unregulated high seas fisheries in the Central Arctic Ocean	International treaty
Ballast Water Management Convention	International treaty
Convention on the Conservation of Antarctic Marine Living Resources	International treaty
MARPOL Convention	International treaty
UN Convention on the Law of the Seas	International treaty
North-East Atlantic Environment Strategy (NEAES)	International policy
Baltic Sea Action Plan (HELCOM)	International policy
Barcelona Action Plan	International policy
Black Sea Strategic Action Plan	International policy
Kunming – Montreal Biodiversity Framework	International policy
Sustainable Development Goals	International policy
UN Ocean Decade	International policy
European Biodiversity Strategy for 2030	EU policy
European Green Deal	EU policy
Integrated Maritime Policy	EU policy
New approach for a sustainable blue economy in the EU	EU policy
Offshore renewable energy strategy	EU policy
Common Fisheries Policy	EU policy
Strategic guidelines for a more sustainable and competitive EU aquaculture for the period 2021-2030	EU policy
Zero pollution action plan	EU policy
Farm to Fork Strategy	EU policy
Recovery Plan for Europe	EU policy
Marine Action Plan (2023)	EU policy
European Climate Regulation	EU law - Regulation
Invasive Alien Species Regulation	EU law - Regulation

REACH Regulation	EU law - Regulation
Recommendation on Integrated Coastal Zone Management in Europe	EU law - non-binding decision or recommendation
Birds Directive	EU law - Directive
EU Nature restoration law (proposed)	EU law - Directive
Habitats Directive	EU law - Directive
Marine Strategy Framework Directive	EU law - Directive
Water Framework Directive	EU law - Directive
Maritime Spatial Planning Directive	EU law - Directive
Single-use Plastics Directive	EU law - Directive

7.2 Annex B – Final list of marine biodiversity related legal and policy instruments analyzed

European Union Directives	Marine Strategy Framework Directive
	Water Framework Directive
	Habitats Directive
	Birds Directive
Regional Seas Conventions and Action Plans	The Helsinki Convention
	The Convention for the Protection of the Marine Environment of the North-East Atlantic
	The Convention for the Protection of the Black Sea Against Pollution
	The Convention for the Protection of the Mediterranean Against Pollution

7.3 Annex C – Data needs categories by MSFD descriptors

Data needs required for reporting categorised by MSFD descriptor and information type for state, pressure and impact-based assessments (European Commission, 2022; Smith *et al.*, 2022). MSFD descriptor assessments correspond and/or are in line with all RSCAPs major thematic and issue-based assessments. MSFD descriptors include where appropriate/possible specific state, pressure and impact criteria (European Commission, 2022).

Data descriptor	Data need	Description	Data type	Information type
Biodiversity	Bycatch	Bycatch mortality of non-commercially exploited fish and shellfish	Biological	Impact
	Captive animals	Number of bottlenose dolphins in captivity.	Biological	Pressure
	Change in community composition	Changes in community composition including changes in phytoplankton biomass and zooplankton abundance.	Biological	Impact
	Change in habitat distribution	Effect of pressure and conservation measures on pelagic and benthic biogenic habitats including proportion of pelagic and benthic biogenic habitat area affected by pressure and trends in habitat distribution/range and condition. Indicators of pelagic habitat condition may include chlorophyll-a concentration and plankton blooms.	Biological	Impact
	Change in population demographics	Effect of pressure and conservation measures on population Including proportion of population affected by pressure and trends in population abundance.	Biological	Impact
	Change in species distribution	Effect of pressure on species including trends in species distribution/range.	Biological	Impact
	Community composition	Species composition (abundance and biomass) of: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • phytoplankton including seasonal trends, diatoms/dinoflagellates biomass ratio in spring and H-Shannon index • zooplankton including H-Shannon index • macrophytobenthos, macroalgae and angiosperms • macrozoobenthos, soft-bottom macrofauna and benthic invertebrate fauna fish species and groups (pelagic, demersal, coastal) 	Biological	State
	Habitat distribution	Pelagic and benthic biogenic habitat distribution/range and condition for pelagic and benthic biogenic habitats listed in instrument documentation. Also includes essential fishing habitats.	Biological	State
	Population demographics	Population demographics of species listed in instrument documentation (e.g. threatened and protected species), plankton and fish communities (coastal, pelagic and demersal) including:	Biological	State

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • population abundance (number of individuals, biomass and/or coverage) • age distribution including age class structure, abundances and size of different lifeforms (e.g. fish larvae) • size distribution including body size and mean maximum length • sex ratio • reproductive indicators including fecundity, breeding success, nestling brood size, pregnancy rate, pup production and measures of reproductive productivity • mortality and survival rate • nutritional status assessed using dead animals (e.g. from bycatch or strandings) 		
	Species distribution	Species distribution and species range for species listed in instrument documentation (e.g. threatened and protected species). Also includes depth limit, area of habitat for species and breeding distribution.	Biological	State
Non-indigenous species	Community composition	Number of species introduced and ratio of indigenous to non-indigenous species.	Biological	Pressure
	Impacts on biota	Proportion of species or habitat impacted by non-indigenous species.	Biological	Impact
	Population demographics	Including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • abundance of established non-indigenous species • trends in abundance trends in arrival/temporal occurrence 	Biological	Pressure
	Species distribution	Species distribution/range and trends in spatial distribution.	Biological	Pressure
Commercially exploited fish and shellfish	Catch	Catch including total landings, landings per species, discards and catch per unit effort.	Biological	Pressure
	Fishing impacts	Includes fishing mortality and number and name of stocks below biological safety limits.	Biological	Impact
	Mariculture	Mariculture production including total production, total production per species.	Biological	Pressure
	Population demographics	Includes: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • number of individuals and biomass • age distribution • size distribution including body size • sex ratio • reproductive indicators including spawning stock biomass, fecundity and recruitment • survival rate 	Biological	State
Marine food webs	Trophic structure	Including abundance, productivity, size distribution and species composition of trophic guilds, and average trophic level of predators.	Biological	State

Eutrophication	Community composition	Species composition and abundance/depth distribution of macrophytes and species composition and abundance of macrofauna.	Biological	Impact
	Harmful algal blooms	Number, extent and duration of harmful algal blooms	Biological	Impact
	Nutrient concentration	Chl a, nitrogen, phosphorus, silicon and oxygen concentration in the water column. Includes nutrient input level from land and atmosphere.	Biological; Chemical	Pressure
	Photic limit	Water transparency of the water column.	Physical	Impact
Seafloor integrity	Change in habitat distribution	Effect of pressure or conservation measures on benthic non-biogenic habitat including proportion of benthic non-biogenic habitat area affected by pressure, spatial extent of adversely affected benthic non-biogenic habitats and trends in benthic non-biogenic habitat distribution/range and condition.	Physical	Impact
	Habitat distribution	Benthic non-biogenic habitat distribution/range and condition for benthic non-biogenic habitats listed in instrument documentation.	Physical	State
	Seafloor disturbance	Spatial extent and distribution of physical loss and disturbance.	Physical	Pressure
	Seafloor structure	Including bathymetry, depth variation and substrate type.	Physical	State
Hydrological conditions	Change in habitat distribution	Spatial extent of adversely affected benthic habitats	Biological; Physical	Impact
	Environmental change	Includes: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • changes in currents • temperature change • change in ice • salinity and precipitation change • sea level change • changes in wave action • change in storms • ocean acidification 	Physical	Pressure
	Environmental state	Includes: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • current speed and direction • temperature • ice thickness • salinity and precipitation • sea level height • significant wave height, wave direction and wave period 	Physical	State

Contaminants	Contaminant concentration	Concentration of contaminants listed in instrument documentation including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • from the atmosphere (e.g. C d, Pb, Hg, dioxines and furans) • from land (e.g. heavy metals) • from sea (e.g. mineral oil/other discharges) • in sediment (e.g. PCBs, PAH, TBT, metals, radionuclides and others) in listed biota (e.g. PFOA, PFOS, PFOSA, PAH, PBDE, HBCDD, TBT, metals and radionuclides)	Chemical	Pressure
	Impacts on biota	Species composition and abundance and habitat condition of adversely affected habitats.	Biological	Impact
	Pollution events	Occurrence, origin, spatial extent and duration of pollution events (e.g. slicks from oil, oil products, hazardous substances, dumped conventional and chemical munitions) including dumping placement of wastes and other matters at sea.	Chemical	Pressure
Contaminants in fish and other seafood	Contaminant concentration	Concentration of contaminants in edible tissues, number of contaminants which have exceeded maximum regulatory levels in commonly consumed seafood and percentage of intestinal enterococci concentration measurements within established standards	Chemical	Pressure
Marine litter	Impacts on biota	Number of adversely affected individuals affected per species including trends in the number of individuals entangled and ingesting litter.	Biological	Impact
	Litter in biota	Amount of litter ingested	Physical	Pressure
	Litter in environment	Composition, amount, spatial distribution of macro-litter and micro-litter including trends in amount of litter washed ashore and/or deposited on coastlines and in the water column and on the seafloor.	Physical	Pressure
Underwater noise and other forms of energy	Noise level	Level of continuous and impulsive noise including spatial distribution (proportion/extent of assessment area) and temporal extent (number/proportion of days).	Physical	Pressure

7.4 Annex D – Keyword searches used for review of academic and grey literature

1. The search terms used for academic literature on google scholar were the following:

"Marine Strategy Framework Directive" and "data gap" and "member state"; "marine" and "data gap" and "Habitats Directive" and "member state"; "marine" and "data gap" and "Birds Directive" and "member state"; "data gap" and "Water Framework Directive" and "member state"; "marine" and "data gap" and "member state" and "Barcelona Convention" or "UNEP-MAP"; "marine" and "data gap" and "member state" and "Bucharest Convention" or "BSIMAP"; "marine" and "data gap" and "member state" and "Helsinki Convention" or "HELCOM" or "BSAP"; "marine" and "data gap" and "member state" and "OSPAR Convention"

Search terms used for searches relating to the EU directives were restricted to the timeframe between 2018 to 2023. This is because this timeframe refers to the latest assessment period.

2. The search terms used for grey literature on google were the following:

"Barcelona Convention" or "UNEP-MAP" and "data gaps" or "information gaps" or "knowledge gaps"; "HELCOM" or "Helsinki convention" and "information gaps" or "data gaps" or "knowledge gaps"; "OSPAR Convention" and "data gaps" or "information gaps" or "knowledge gaps"; "Bucharest convention" or "Convention on the Protection of the Black Sea against Pollution" and "data gaps" or "information gaps" or "knowledge gaps"; "Birds Directive" and "data gaps" or "information gaps" or "knowledge gaps"; "Habitats Directive" and "information gaps" or "data gaps" or "knowledge gaps"; "Marine Strategy Framework Directive" or "MSFD" and "data gaps" or "information gaps" or "knowledge gaps"; "Water Framework Directive" or "WFD" and "data gaps" or "information gaps" or "knowledge gaps".

After relevant grey literature was collected from google web searches using the above search terms, the specific websites relating to the EU (in the case of the directives) or the Regional Sea Convention Secretariats were used for further searches to find relevant grey literature on gaps in marine policy.

The websites used to find relevant grey literature relating to EU and RSCAPs are as follows:

(EU) <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/search.html?name=collection%3Aeu-law&type=named&qid=1608210908077>

(Barcelona Convention) <https://www.unep.org/unepmap/who-we-are/barcelona-convention-and-protocols>

(Helsinki Convention) <https://helcom.fi/>

(OSPAR Convention) <https://www.ospar.org/>

(Bucharest convention) http://www.blacksea-commission.org/_convention.asp

7.5 Annex E - Data needs required for reporting for European marine biodiversity-related Directives and Regional Sea Conventions categorised by MSFD descriptor

2023